

IMPROVING MATHEMATICAL LITERACY OF STUDENTS THROUGH DEVELOPING PISA COMPETENCES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article aims to improve students' mathematical literacy through the formation of PISA (Programme for International Student Assessment) competencies in primary education. The article analyzes the importance of mathematical competences, methods of their development, and data obtained from PISA studies. Also, practical examples, teaching methods and innovative programs are shown in improving students' mathematical literacy. This approach helps to develop students' logical thinking and problem solving skills. As a result, the article presents recommendations aimed at strengthening students' mathematical knowledge and improving their global educational performance.*

Keywords: *mathematical knowledge, improving the quality of education, teaching methods, student literacy, international assessment system, mathematical literacy, mathematical requirements, implementation.*

It is important to suggest that the study collected information that allows us to obtain information about the uniqueness of the education system of the participating countries. In addition, PISA is the only international research program to assess the knowledge and skills of 15-year-old schoolchildren. The main reason for conducting a study among 15-year-old schoolchildren is that in most OECD countries this age is the final stage of compulsory education. At this point, the natural question is: "What does Uzbekistan's participation in these studies give?" Participation in the PISA study provides an opportunity: "General education is our highest mission to bring children to success, our goal is to see them happy. Definitely, this project is an important step towards realizing our high mission by providing quality education in primary grades," said Deputy Minister of Public Education Rustam Karimzhonov. The article presents the results of our study of some aspects of the formation of mathematical literacy in students. Providing a working definition of mathematical literacy, the study identifies four components of mathematical literacy. The formation of each component of mathematical literacy is determined by its structural features. The characteristics of the first component of the program are the acquisition of special and general educational cognitive knowledge, skills, abilities and methods of educational activities, teaching methods.

The second component is determined by the ability to quickly and widely generalize mathematical objects, relationships, actions, freely adjust the thought process, move from direct thinking to reverse, sequential, correct, separate logical thinking, formalized perception of mathematical material, the structure of the problem statement, features of the third component, the ability to formulate and write problems in the language of mathematics and the results of the solution. The fourth component is expressed in the implementation of the previous components in life situations. In our country, special attention is paid to the radical reform of the education

system, the acquisition of modern knowledge and skills at the level of world standards, the growth of physically and mentally mature people, the development of their abilities and talents, intellectual abilities. work is underway to reveal their potential, to cultivate in the hearts of the younger generation a sense of loyalty and devotion to the Motherland. In the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, dated February 7, 2017 "On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" the improvement of the social sphere, in particular, the sphere of education and science, and in the address to Oliy Majlis dated January 24, 2020 the tasks of adequate preparation for the international assessment processes in 2021 were defined.

At present time there are influential international organizations that conduct research to assess the achievements of the education system of countries of the world and help in the implementation of reforms. It is important that Uzbekistan's participation in these studies and their results are recognized in the world community, so that the younger generation can learn new innovative methods based on international experience, and so that they can effectively apply their knowledge in practice. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) conducts research to find solutions to problems arising in different fields.

In particular, on the basis of this organization, the international program for assessing the literacy of students PISA (The Program for International Student Assessment) was developed in order to develop general secondary education, which is the main link in the educational system. The reason for the economic organization's appeal to the field of education is that personnel for any field grows primarily in schools and ordinary classes. In this sense, the OECD organization sought to compile a rating of how much money member states spend on the education system and how effective it is. Later, the interest of other countries in these studies increased, and today the number of member states of the organization is increasing.

By 2030, the Republic of Uzbekistan will be among the first 30 advanced countries in the world according to the rating of the international PISA program, as well as by conducting international studies in the field of assessing the quality of education in the public education system, student reading, mathematics. and the tasks of creating a national system aimed at assessing the level of literacy in the field of natural sciences were determined.

Within the framework of the concept of development of the public education system until 2030 with a special emphasis on the development of critical thinking of students, independent search for information, analytical skills and competencies, general education programs are being developed that meet the requirements of the modern innovative economy and new public education. It is envisaged to introduce standards, constant participation in international tests PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS and other tests to assess the quality of students' knowledge. International assessment program (PISA), the Program for the International Assessment of Primary School Reading Comprehension (PIRLS), the Program for the Assessment of Student Performance in Mathematics and Science , the head and teacher began to participate in the programs of international assessment of the teaching and learning environment and their working conditions (TALIS) in general education institutions. For this purpose, the National Center for the Implementation of International Studies on Education Quality Assessment was established under the State Inspectorate for Education Quality under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For participating as a representative of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the organization and coordination of international studies at the National Center, to ensure the successful

participation of general secondary education institutions in international studies, to carry out systematic monitoring of the implementation of international assessment programs at the National Center educational process, the task was set to prepare educational recommendations for improving the qualifications of teachers in reading, mathematics and natural sciences using innovative teaching methods. International assessment programs such as PISA, aimed at assessing the quality of education, are being conducted in Uzbekistan for the first time, so their transparent and objective implementation imposes great responsibility on employees in the field. In this regard, previously, it was prepared in order to enrich the understanding of the teaching staff about international studies, thereby contributing to improving the quality of education. The bulletin was prepared as a logical continuation of methodological manuals, a collection of tasks, notebooks.

By summerising it should be suggested that mathematical literacy is a person's ability to think mathematically about various life situations (contexts) and issues, express a given problem using mathematics, use mathematics to solve a problem, use the obtained results to interpret and evaluate the solution to a problem. It includes concepts, algorithms, facts and tools for describing, explaining and predicting events. It helps people understand the place of mathematics in the world and make the informed judgments and decisions needed to be creative, inquisitive, and reflective citizens of the 21st century.

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